

Long-term trends in abundance, phenology, and morphometrics of Little Stint *Calidris minuta* during autumn migration in southern Sweden, 1946–2020

Jonas Waldenström, Mariëlle van Toor, Åke Lindström

Session set-up

Packages used for the analyses and visualisation of data:

```
# packages used for data and timestamp organisation
library(plyr)
library(lubridate)

# packages used for data visualisation
library(ggplot2)
library(patchwork)

# calculation running means
library(zoo)

# models, model evaluation, and visualisation
library(lme4)
library(glmmTMB)
library(DHARMA)
library(sjPlot)
library(interactions)

# hexcodes for the colour scheme used to highlight age classes
colour.scheme=c('Adult'='#f77d0f', 'Juvenile'='#542788', 'Unaged'='grey40')
```

R version 4.3.0 (2023-04-21)
Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu (64-bit)
Running under: Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS

Matrix products: default
BLAS: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/blas/libblas.so.3.9.0
LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/lapack/liblapack.so.3.9.0

locale:
[1] LC_CTYPE=en_US.UTF-8 LC_NUMERIC=C
[3] LC_TIME=en_US.UTF-8 LC_COLLATE=en_US.UTF-8
[5] LC_MONETARY=en_US.UTF-8 LC_MESSAGES=en_US.UTF-8
[7] LC_PAPER=sv_SE.UTF-8 LC_NAME=C
[9] LC_ADDRESS=C LC_TELEPHONE=C
[11] LC_MEASUREMENT=sv_SE.UTF-8 LC_IDENTIFICATION=C

time zone: Europe/Stockholm
tzcode source: system (glibc)

attached base packages:
[1] stats graphics grDevices utils datasets methods base

other attached packages:
[1] interactions_1.1.5 sjPlot_2.8.14 DHARMA_0.4.6 glmmTMB_1.1.7
[5] lme4_1.1-32 Matrix_1.5-4 zoo_1.8-12 patchwork_1.1.2
[9] ggplot2_3.4.2 lubridate_1.9.2 plyr_1.8.8

loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
[1] gtable_0.3.3 TMB_1.9.4 xfun_0.39
[4] bayestestR_0.13.1 insight_0.19.1 lattice_0.21-8
[7] numDeriv_2016.8-1.1 vctr_0.6.2 tools_4.3.0
[10] sjstats_0.18.2 generics_0.1.3 sandwich_3.0-2
[13] tibble_3.2.1 fansi_1.0.4 pkgconfig_2.0.3
[16] ggeffects_1.2.1 lifecycle_1.0.3 compiler_4.3.0
[19] sjmisc_2.8.9 munsell_0.5.0 codetools_0.2-19
[22] htmltools_0.5.5 yaml_2.3.7 crayon_1.5.2
[25] pillar_1.9.0 nloptr_2.0.3 tidyr_1.3.0
[28] MASS_7.3-59 boot_1.3-28.1 multcomp_1.4-23
[31] nlme_3.1-162 tidyselect_1.2.0 sjlabelled_1.2.0
[34] digest_0.6.31 performance_0.10.3 mvtnorm_1.1-3
[37] pander_0.6.5 dplyr_1.1.2 purrr_1.0.1
[40] splines_4.3.0 fastmap_1.1.1 grid_4.3.0
[43] colorspace_2.1-0 cli_3.6.1 magrittr_2.0.3

[46]	survival_3.5-5	utf8_1.2.3	broom_1.0.4
[49]	TH.data_1.1-2	withr_2.5.0	jtools_2.2.1
[52]	scales_1.2.1	backports_1.4.1	estimability_1.4.1
[55]	timechange_0.2.0	rmarkdown_2.21	modelr_0.1.11
[58]	emmeans_1.8.5	coda_0.19-4	evaluate_0.20
[61]	knitr_1.42	rlang_1.1.0	Rcpp_1.0.10
[64]	xtable_1.8-4	glue_1.6.2	rstudioapi_0.14
[67]	minqa_1.2.5	jsonlite_1.8.4	R6_2.5.1

Data import

Full data set of banding records from the Ottenby Bird Observatory from 1946 – 2020:

```
# read data set
stints <- read.delim('data/ring_recoveries/recoveries_corrected.csv', sep='\t', header=T)

# convert date to YYYY-MM-DD format
stints$date <- paste(stints$YR,
                    sprintf('%.2d', stints$MN),
                    sprintf('%.2d', stints$DY), sep='-')

# determine ordinal day of the year
stints$julian.day <- as.numeric(strftime(stints$date, format='%j'))

# set date column to Date-format
stints$date <- as.Date(stints$date)

str(stints)
```

```
'data.frame':  4791 obs. of  18 variables:
 $ RINGNR      : chr  " 2835891" " 2835892" " 2835893" " 215178" ...
 $ LOCALCODE   : chr  "01" "01" "01" "VADA" ...
 $ TR          : int  1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 ...
 $ YR          : int  1994 1994 1994 1959 2019 2019 2019 2018 2019 1950 ...
 $ MN          : int  6 6 6 7 7 7 7 7 7 7 ...
 $ DY          : int  25 25 26 7 8 9 9 10 13 13 ...
 $ HOUR        : int  22 22 7 NA 23 7 7 17 19 NA ...
 $ Date        : chr  "25/Jun" "25/Jun" "26/Jun" "7/Jul" ...
 $ ART         : chr  "SMSNÄ" "SMSNÄ" "SMSNÄ" "SMSNÄ" ...
 $ SIGNATURE   : chr  "MRG" "MRG" "NJN" "XXX" ...
 $ SEX         : chr  "" "" "" "" ...
```

```

$ AGE_1      : chr  "20" "20" "20" "1+" ...
$ Age       : chr  "Adult" "Adult" "Adult" "Unaged" ...
$ WING      : int   99 94 96 NA 96 102 97 100 97 NA ...
$ VIKT      : num   24.6 23.5 23.7 NA 20.6 25.2 21.8 27.3 31.8 NA ...
$ FETT      : int   NA NA NA NA 3 2 1 2 4 NA ...
$ date      : Date, format: "1994-06-25" "1994-06-25" ...
$ julian.day: num   176 176 177 188 189 190 190 191 194 194 ...

```

Data containing mass gain between initial capture and recapture (23 individuals):

```

# read data set
mg <- read.delim('data/ring_recoveries/stint_lbm_recapture.csv')

# extract mark and recapture dates in data, and set to Date-format
mg$mark.date <-
  as.Date(unlist(lapply(strsplit(mg$Ring_day, '\\/'), function(x){
    paste(x[3], x[1], x[2], sep='-')
  })))
mg$recapture.date <-
  as.Date(unlist(lapply(strsplit(mg$Recapture_day, '\\/'), function(x){
    paste(x[3], x[1], x[2], sep='-')
  })))

str(mg)

```

```

'data.frame':  23 obs. of  12 variables:
 $ Individual      : chr  "2835542" "2835580" "2835414" "2835599" ...
 $ Ring_day       : chr  "8/10/1989" "9/1/1989" "8/19/1988" "8/15/1990" ...
 $ Recapture_day  : chr  "8/12/1989" "9/3/1989" "8/26/1988" "8/19/1990" ...
 $ Days.passed    : int   2 2 7 4 5 4 4 3 2 1 ...
 $ Initial.body.mass : num   23.4 25 19.7 27.8 24.6 24.1 25.5 25.3 22.5 21.8 ...
 $ Body.mass.at.recapture: num   23.5 22.2 27.6 32 25.7 28.3 31.9 31.2 24.4 22.2 ...
 $ Difference..g.  : num   0.1 -2.8 7.9 4.2 1.1 ...
 $ Diff           : num   0.005 -0.14 0.395 0.21 0.055 0.21 0.32 0.295 0.095 0.02 ...
 $ Diff..LBM      : chr  "0.5%" "-14.0%" "39.5%" "21.0%" ...
 $ Diff..LBM.day  : chr  "0.3%" "-7.0%" "5.6%" "5.3%" ...
 $ mark.date      : Date, format: "1989-08-10" "1989-09-01" ...
 $ recapture.date : Date, format: "1989-08-12" "1989-09-03" ...

```

Abundance

Plot abundance histogram over the entire study period, split into adults (A), juveniles (B), and individuals of unknown age (C):

```
# base plot
p <- ggplot() +
  scale_x_continuous(name='', breaks=seq(1945, 2020, 5)) +
  theme_light() + labs(x='', y='')

# individual plots for each age class
p.adult <- p +
  geom_bar(data=stints[stints$Age=='Adult',], aes(x=YR), fill='grey90', colour='grey40')
p.juvenile <- p +
  geom_bar(data=stints[stints$Age=='Juvenile',], aes(x=YR), fill='grey90', colour='grey40')
p.unaged <- p +
  geom_bar(data=stints[stints$Age=='Unaged',], aes(x=YR), fill='grey90', colour='grey40')

# combine plots into a single figure
p.adult + p.juvenile + p.unaged +
  plot_layout(ncol=1, heights=c(0.2, 0.5, 0.3)) +
  plot_annotation(tag_level='A')
```


Calculate a running median, 25%- and 75%-quartiles for the number of adult and juvenile+unaged birds trapped over the study year period, using a window size of 15 years:

```

# group juveniles and unaged individuals into a shared category
stints$age.mod <- ifelse(stints$Age=='Adult', 'Adult', 'Juvenile')

# count the number of adult and juvenile + unaged birds captures for each year
counts <- ddply(stints, c('YR', 'age.mod'), function(tmp){
  data.frame(n=nrow(tmp))
})

# calculate running median + quartiles over a 15-year window
new <- ddply(counts, 'age.mod', function(x){
  new <- expand.grid(YR=1946:2020)
  x <- merge(new, x, all=T)
  x$age.mod[is.na(x$age.mod)] <- unique(x$age.mod[!is.na(x$age.mod)])
  x$n[is.na(x$n)] <- 0
  x$median <- rollapply(x$n, width=15, FUN=median, partial=T)
  x$q25 <- rollapply(x$n, width=15, FUN=quantile, probs=0.25, partial=T)
  x$q75 <- rollapply(x$n, width=15, FUN=quantile, probs=0.75, partial=T)
  x$partial <- is.na(rollapply(x$n, width=15, FUN=median, fill=NA, partial=F))
  return(x)
})

str(new)

```

```

'data.frame': 150 obs. of 7 variables:
 $ YR      : int  1946 1947 1948 1949 1950 1951 1952 1953 1954 1955 ...
 $ age.mod: chr  "Adult" "Adult" "Adult" "Adult" ...
 $ n       : num  0 0 2 0 4 2 4 0 6 0 ...
 $ median  : num  1 2 1 2 1.5 2 1.5 1 2 2 ...
 $ q25     : num  0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 ...
 $ q75     : num  2.5 4 3.5 4 4 4 4 4 4 4 ...
 $ partial: logi  TRUE TRUE TRUE TRUE TRUE TRUE ...

```

Plot the resulting data:

```

adult <- new[new$age.mod=='Adult',]
juvenile <- new[new$age.mod=='Juvenile',]

ggplot(adult) +
  geom_ribbon(data=adult[6:(nrow(adult)-6),],
            aes(x=YR, ymin=q25, ymax=q75), colour=NA, alpha=0.3) +
  geom_line(data=adult[6:(nrow(adult)-6),], aes(x=YR, y=median)) +

```

```

geom_point(aes(x=YR, y=n), size=0.5) +
theme_light() +
theme(axis.title.x=element_blank()) +
labs(x='', y='Number of individuals', title='Adult individuals') +
ggplot(juvenile) +
geom_ribbon(data=juvenile[6:(nrow(juvenile)-6),],
          aes(x=YR, ymin=q25, ymax=q75), colour=NA, alpha=0.3) +
geom_line(data=juvenile[6:(nrow(juvenile)-6),], aes(x=YR, y=median)) +
geom_point(aes(x=YR, y=n), size=0.5) +
theme_light() +
labs(x='', y='', title='Juvenile individuals') +
theme(axis.title=element_blank()) +
plot_layout(ncol=2)

```


Define model for estimating how the mean abundance of juvenile and adult little stints changed over the study period (individuals with unknown age are excluded from the model).

```

# again, calculate counts of birds captured for each year
counts <- ddply(stints, c('YR', 'Age'), function(tmp){
  data.frame(n=nrow(tmp))
})
# year as year of capture instead (ranges from 1 to 75)
counts$year <- counts$YR-1945

```

```

# calculate the natural log of number of birds + 1
counts$log.n <- log1p(counts$n)

# exclude unaged individuals
model.data <- counts[counts$Age!='Unaged',]

# linear regression assuming normal error distribution
m <- lm(log.n~year*Age+0, data=model.data)

summary(m)

```

Call:

```
lm(formula = log.n ~ year * Age + 0, data = model.data)
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.3332	-0.7917	-0.1042	0.8153	3.0746

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
year	0.0003266	0.0079622	0.041	0.96735
AgeAdult	1.4811620	0.3502654	4.229	4.94e-05 ***
AgeJuvenile	4.2209604	0.3160863	13.354	< 2e-16 ***
year:AgeJuvenile	-0.0327563	0.0109794	-2.983	0.00352 **

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 1.193 on 108 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.8203, Adjusted R-squared: 0.8136

F-statistic: 123.2 on 4 and 108 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16

Plot the evaluation and visualisation from the model:

```

# plain residuals
hist(residuals(m))

```

Histogram of residuals(m)


```
# simulating residuals from the model using the DHARMA-package  
res.sim <- simulateResiduals(m)  
  
# Quantile-quantile plot:  
plotQQunif(res.sim)
```

QQ plot residuals


```

# define breaks & labels for the y-axis of plot
breaks <- log1p(c(0,5,10,25,50,100,250,500)+1)
labels <- c(0,5,10,25,50,100,250,500)

# plot interaction
interact_plot(m, 'year', 'Age', plot.points=T, interval=T,
             colors=colour.scheme[1:2], outcome.scale='response',
             data=counts[counts$Age!='Unaged',]) +
theme_light() +
scale_y_continuous(name='N (individuals)', breaks=breaks, labels=labels) +
scale_x_continuous(name='', breaks=seq(0,75,10), labels=seq(1945,2020,10))

```


Phenology

An initial look at capture dates of adults (A), juveniles (B), and individuals of unknown age (C):

```

# format dates for labelling the x-axis
dates <- as.Date(c('2018-06-15', '2018-07-01', '2018-07-15', '2018-08-01',
                  '2018-08-15', '2018-09-01', '2018-09-15', '2018-10-01',
                  '2018-10-15'))
breaks <- as.numeric(strftime(dates, format='%j'))

```

```

labels <- paste(sprintf('%.2d', day(dates)), month(dates, label=T, abbr=T), sep=' ')

# calculate median capture date per age group (+ quartiles)
summary.date <- ddply(stints, 'Age', function(x){
  y <- ifelse(unique(x$Age)=='Adult', 13,
             ifelse(unique(x$Age)=='Juvenile', 290, 95))
  height <- ifelse(unique(x$Age)=='Adult', 1.5,
                  ifelse(unique(x$Age)=='Juvenile', 25, 10))
  data.frame(y=y, height=height, median=median(x$julian.day),
            q25=quantile(x$julian.day, .25), q75=quantile(x$julian.day, .75),
            mean=round(mean(x$julian.day), 2), sd=round(sd(x$julian.day), 2))
})

# one panel for each age class
p.adult <- ggplot(stints[stints$Age=='Adult',]) +
  geom_bar(aes(x=julian.day), fill='grey90', colour='grey40') +
  geom_errorbarh(data=summary.date[summary.date$Age=='Adult',],
                aes(xmin=mean-sd, xmax=mean+sd, y=y, height=height)) +
  geom_point(data=summary.date[summary.date$Age=='Adult',], aes(x=mean, y=y)) +
  labs(x='', y='') +
  scale_x_continuous(breaks=breaks, labels=labels) +
  theme_light()

p.juvenile <- ggplot(stints[stints$Age=='Juvenile',]) +
  geom_bar(aes(x=julian.day), fill='grey90', colour='grey40') +
  geom_errorbarh(data=summary.date[summary.date$Age=='Juvenile',],
                aes(xmin=mean-sd, xmax=mean+sd, y=y, height=height)) +
  geom_point(data=summary.date[summary.date$Age=='Juvenile',], aes(x=mean, y=y)) +
  labs(x='', y='') +
  scale_x_continuous(breaks=breaks, labels=labels) +
  theme_light()

p.unaged <- ggplot(stints[stints$Age=='Unaged',]) +
  geom_bar(aes(x=julian.day), fill='grey90', colour='grey40') +
  geom_errorbarh(data=summary.date[summary.date$Age=='Unaged',],
                aes(xmin=mean-sd, xmax=mean+sd, y=y, height=height)) +
  geom_point(data=summary.date[summary.date$Age=='Unaged',], aes(x=mean, y=y)) +
  labs(x='Date', y='') +
  scale_x_continuous(breaks=breaks, labels=labels) +
  theme_light()

```

```
p.all <- p.adult + p.juvenile + p.unaged +
  plot_layout(ncol=1, heights=c(0.2, 0.5, 0.3)) +
  plot_annotation(tag_levels='A')

# combine plots into a single figure:
print('Timing, overall')
```

```
[1] "Timing, overall"
```

```
print(p.all)
```


Plot to see whether we can visually distinguish a trend in capture date over the study period:

```
ggplot(stints, aes(x=YR, y=julian.day, colour=Age)) +
  geom_point() + scale_colour_manual(values=colour.scheme) +
  theme_light() +
  scale_x_continuous(name='', breaks=seq(1945, 2020, 5)) +
  scale_y_continuous(name='Marking date', breaks=breaks, labels=labels) +
  theme(legend.position='bottom') +
  facet_wrap(~Age, ncol=1)
```


Age ● Adult ● Juvenile ● Unaged

Fitting a linear mixed-effects regression model to estimate how the mean capture date per age class varies with year. We included year as a random effect to take additional sources of variation into account (e.g. if one year had a particularly early/late spring). Since the variance around the mean capture date differs between age classes, we included a dispersion formula to estimate variance as well as the mean capture date for both adult and juvenile individuals. Because the time series for unaged individuals is much shorter, they will be excluded from the model.

```
# exclude individuals of unknown age
tmp <- stints[stints$Age!='Unaged',]

# convert to year of study (from 1-75)
tmp$year <- tmp$YR - 1945

# model
m2 <- glmmTMB(julian.day ~ year*Age + 0 + (1|YR/Age), data=tmp, dispformula=~Age)
summary(m2)
```

```
Family: gaussian ( identity )
Formula:          julian.day ~ year * Age + 0 + (1 | YR/Age)
Dispersion:              ~Age
Data: tmp
```

```
      AIC      BIC  logLik deviance df.resid
28779.5 28830.0 -14381.7 28763.5     4060
```

Random effects:

Conditional model:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
Age:YR	(Intercept)	84.449	9.190
YR	(Intercept)	4.949	2.225
Residual		NA	NA

Number of obs: 4068, groups: Age:YR, 112; YR, 68

Conditional model:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
year	-0.44894	0.07617	-5.89	3.77e-09 ***
AgeAdult	234.08796	3.35396	69.79	< 2e-16 ***
AgeJuvenile	244.71876	2.63117	93.01	< 2e-16 ***
year:AgeJuvenile	0.42595	0.09849	4.32	1.53e-05 ***

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Dispersion model:

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	4.6647	0.1055	44.23	< 2e-16 ***
AgeJuvenile	-0.5289	0.1079	-4.90	9.54e-07 ***

```
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Some model evaluation & visualisation:

```
# plain residuals  
hist(residuals(m2))
```

Histogram of residuals(m2)


```
# simulating residuals from the model using the DHARMA-package  
res.sim <- simulateResiduals(m2)
```

```
# Quantile-quantile plot:  
plotQQunif(res.sim)
```



```
# plotting model effect estimates along with the underlying data:
p <- interact_plot(m2, 'year', 'Age', plot.points=T, interval=T,
                  colors=colour.scheme[-3], data=tmp) + #partial.residuals=T
theme_light() + labs(x='Year', y='Capture date') +
scale_x_continuous(breaks=seq(0,75,10), labels=seq(1945,2020,10)) +
scale_y_continuous(breaks=breaks, labels=labels) +
  guides(colour=guide_none(),
         linetype=guide_none(),
         fill=guide_none()) +
facet_wrap(~factor(Age, labels=c('Adult individuals', 'Juvenile individuals')),
          ncol=2) + theme_light() +
theme(legend.position='bottom', axis.title.x=element_blank(),
      strip.background = element_rect(fill='white'),
      strip.text=element_text(colour='black', size=11))

print(p)
```


Body size

Body mass

```
# subset data to individuals of known age & body mass
tmp <- stints[!is.na(stints$VIKT) & stints$Age %in% c('Adult', 'Juvenile'),]

# calculate median + quartiles for body mass of adults and juveniles
summary.mass <- ddply(tmp, 'Age', function(x){
  y <- ifelse(unique(x$Age)=='Adult', 19, 110)
  height <- ifelse(unique(x$Age)=='Adult', 2, 11)
  data.frame(y=y, height=height, median=median(x$VIKT),
             q25=quantile(x$VIKT, .25), q75=quantile(x$VIKT, .75),
             min=min(x$VIKT), max=max(x$VIKT),
             mean=round(mean(x$VIKT), 2), sd=round(sd(x$VIKT), 2))
  })

# print summary
print(summary.mass[, -c(1:2)])
```

```
height median q25    q75 min  max mean  sd
1         2  26.05  24 28.375 20.1 35.7 26.42 3.21
```

2 11 25.10 23 28.275 15.3 39.0 25.87 3.79

Plot data on body mass as shown in manuscript, with adults in panel A and juveniles in panel B:

```
# one panel per age class
p.adult <- ggplot(tmp[tmp$Age=='Adult',]) +
  geom_histogram(aes(x=VIKT), fill='grey90', colour='grey40', binwidth=1) +
  geom_errorbarh(data=summary.mass[summary.mass$Age=='Adult',],
                aes(xmin=mean-sd, xmax=mean+sd, y=y, height=height)) +
  geom_point(data=summary.mass[summary.mass$Age=='Adult',], aes(x=mean, y=y)) +
  labs(x='', y='') + theme_light() +
  scale_x_continuous(limits=c(15, 40), expand=c(0,0))

p.juvenile <- ggplot(tmp[tmp$Age=='Juvenile',]) +
  geom_histogram(aes(x=VIKT), fill='grey90', colour='grey40', binwidth=1) +
  geom_errorbarh(data=summary.mass[summary.mass$Age=='Juvenile',],
                aes(xmin=mean-sd, xmax=mean+sd, y=y, height=height)) +
  geom_point(data=summary.mass[summary.mass$Age=='Juvenile',], aes(x=mean, y=y)) +
  labs(x='Body mass (g)', y='') + theme_light() +
  scale_x_continuous(limits=c(15, 40), expand=c(0,0))

# combine panels into single figure
p.all <- p.adult + p.juvenile + plot_layout(ncol=1, heights=c(0.4, 0.6)) + plot_annotation

# print figure
print('morphology_bodymass')
```

[1] "morphology_bodymass"

```
print(p.all)
```


Wing length

We excluded individuals of unknown age from the analysis:

```
# subset data to individuals of known age & wing length
tmp <- stints[!is.na(stints$WING) & stints$Age %in% c('Adult', 'Juvenile'),]

# calculate median + quartiles for wing length of adults and juveniles
summary.wing <- ddply(tmp, 'Age', function(x){
  y <- ifelse(unique(x$Age)=='Adult', 19, 190)
  height <- ifelse(unique(x$Age)=='Adult', 2, 20)
  data.frame(y=y, height=height, median=median(x$WING),
             q25=quantile(x$WING, .25), q75=quantile(x$WING, .75),
             mean=round(mean(x$WING), 2), sd=round(sd(x$WING), 2))
  })

# print summary
summary.wing[,]
```

	Age	y	height	median	q25	q75	mean	sd
1	Adult	19	2	99	97	101	98.93	3.39
2	Juvenile	190	20	100	98	102	99.77	2.75

```
# estimated difference between mean wing length of adults & juveniles:
m3 <- lm(WING~Age+1, data=stints[!is.na(stints$WING),])
summary(m3)
```

Call:

```
lm(formula = WING ~ Age + 1, data = stints[!is.na(stints$WING),
])
```

Residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-8.7704	-1.7704	0.2296	2.2296	13.0714

Coefficients:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	98.9286	0.2510	394.142	< 2e-16 ***
AgeJuvenile	0.8418	0.2651	3.176	0.00153 **
AgeUnaged	0.4048	1.6459	0.246	0.80578

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 2.817 on 1219 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.008243, Adjusted R-squared: 0.006615

F-statistic: 5.066 on 2 and 1219 DF, p-value: 0.006443

```
hist(residuals(m3))
```

Histogram of residuals(m3)


```
plot(simulateResiduals(m3))
```

DHARMA residual

Plot data as shown in manuscript, with adults in panel A and juveniles in panel B:

```
# one panel for adults and juveniles each:
p.adult <- ggplot(tmp[tmp$Age=='Adult',]) +
```

```

geom_histogram(aes(x=WING), fill='grey90', colour='grey40', binwidth=1) +
geom_errorbarh(data=summary.wing[summary.wing$Age=='Adult',],
               aes(xmin=mean-sd, xmax=mean+sd, y=y, height=height)) +
geom_point(data=summary.wing[summary.wing$Age=='Adult',], aes(x=mean, y=y)) +
labs(x='', y='') + theme_light() +
scale_x_continuous(limits=c(90,112), expand=c(0,0))

p.juvenile <- ggplot(tmp[tmp$Age=='Juvenile',]) +
geom_histogram(aes(x=WING), fill='grey90', colour='grey40', binwidth=1) +
geom_errorbarh(data=summary.wing[summary.wing$Age=='Juvenile',],
               aes(xmin=mean-sd, xmax=mean+sd, y=y, height=height)) +
geom_point(data=summary.wing[summary.wing$Age=='Juvenile',], aes(x=mean, y=y)) +
labs(x='Wing length (mm)', y='') + theme_light() +
scale_x_continuous(limits=c(90,112), expand=c(0,0))

# combine panels into one figure
p.all <- p.adult + p.juvenile + plot_layout(ncol=1, heights=c(0.4, 0.6)) +
plot_annotation(tag_levels='A')

# print figure
print('morphology_winglength')

```

```
[1] "morphology_winglength"
```

```
print(p.all)
```


Body mass, fat scores, and fuel deposition

Fat scores and body mass

Plot frequency of fat scores in capture data:

```
# select observations associated with a fat score
tmp <- stints[!is.na(stints$FETT),]
tmp$fat.score <- factor(tmp$FETT, levels=1:9)
```

```
table(tmp$Age)
```

```
Adult Juvenile
55      58
```

```
# one panel per age class (no observations for unaged birds with fat score)
p.adult <- ggplot(tmp[tmp$Age=='Adult',]) +
  geom_bar(aes(x=fat.score), fill='grey90', colour='grey40') +
  labs(x='', y='') +
  theme_bw() + scale_x_discrete(drop=FALSE)
```

```

p.juvenile <- ggplot(tmp[tmp$Age=='Juvenile',]) +
  geom_bar(aes(x=fat.score), fill='grey90', colour='grey40') +
  labs(x='Fat score', y='') +
  theme_bw() + scale_x_discrete(drop=FALSE)

# combine panels (A=adults, B=juveniles)
p.adult + p.juvenile + plot_layout(ncol=1, heights=c(0.5, 0.5)) + plot_annotation(tag_level=

```


Plot how body mass relates to fat score:

```

# calculate median & quartiles in body mass for each age & fat score
summary.fat <- ddply(tmp, c('Age', 'FETT'), function(x){
  data.frame(median=median(x$VIKT, na.rm=T),
             q25=quantile(x$VIKT, 0.25, na.rm=T),
             q75=quantile(x$VIKT, 0.75, na.rm=T))
})

summary.fat$fat.score <- factor(summary.fat$FETT, levels=1:9)

ggplot(tmp, aes(x=factor(FETT))) +
  geom_pointrange(data=summary.fat, aes(y=median, ymin=q25, ymax=q75, fill=Age),
                 position=position_dodge(width=0.5), shape=21) +

```

```
geom_jitter(aes(y=VIKT, colour=Age), width=0.3, alpha=0.7) +
scale_colour_manual(values=colour.scheme) +
scale_fill_manual(values=colour.scheme) +
labs(x='Fat score', y='Body mass (g)') +
theme_light()
```


Fit two linear regression models to estimate how mean body mass changes with fat score. We here provide two alternatives:

- fat score as continuous predictor
- fat score as ordinal ranks (more appropriate because we don't know whether the increase in body mass for each increase in fat class is equal)

We here estimate how mean body mass changes with fat score, and account for the overall size of the bird by including wing length in an interaction with fat score. We further include ringer ID as a random effect to account for potential consistent differences in measuring between ringers.

```
# select individuals for which body mass and fat score are available:
tmp <- stints[complete.cases(stints[,c('VIKT', 'FETT')]),]

# wing length is available for all of these individuals
```

```
table(!is.na(tmp$WING))
```

```
TRUE  
113
```

```
# alternative 1: fat score as a continuous predictor  
ma <- lmer(VIKT ~ FETT * WING + (1|SIGNATURE), data=tmp)  
summary(ma)
```

```
Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']  
Formula: VIKT ~ FETT * WING + (1 | SIGNATURE)  
Data: tmp
```

```
REML criterion at convergence: 527.5
```

```
Scaled residuals:
```

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.3274	-0.6861	-0.1168	0.6025	2.9535

```
Random effects:
```

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
SIGNATURE	(Intercept)	0.3314	0.5757
	Residual	5.6140	2.3694

```
Number of obs: 113, groups: SIGNATURE, 33
```

```
Fixed effects:
```

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value
(Intercept)	6.39141	22.51577	0.284
FETT	-4.58237	5.08704	-0.901
WING	0.15000	0.22593	0.664
FETT:WING	0.05694	0.05091	1.118

```
Correlation of Fixed Effects:
```

	(Intr)	FETT	WING
FETT		-0.935	
WING	-1.000		0.933
FETT:WING	0.935	-1.000	-0.935


```
#####
# alternative 2: fat score as a ordinal ranked predictor
tmp$fat.ordinal <- factor(tmp$FETT, levels=1:9, ordered=T)
table(tmp$fat.ordinal)
```

```
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
4 16 18 20 31 18 5 1 0
```

```
mb <- lmer(VIKT ~ fat.ordinal * WING + (1|SIGNATURE), data=tmp)
```

fixed-effect model matrix is rank deficient so dropping 1 column / coefficient

boundary (singular) fit: see help('isSingular')

```
summary(mb)
```

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: VIKT ~ fat.ordinal * WING + (1 | SIGNATURE)
Data: tmp

REML criterion at convergence: 496.7

Scaled residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.0335	-0.6089	-0.1118	0.4045	2.4432

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
SIGNATURE	(Intercept)	0.000	0.000
	Residual	5.816	2.412

Number of obs: 113, groups: SIGNATURE, 33

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value
(Intercept)	-343.4906	148.0948	-2.319
fat.ordinal.L	-1488.2353	643.8397	-2.311
fat.ordinal.Q	-1456.5723	647.9350	-2.248
fat.ordinal.C	-1148.9458	510.8492	-2.249
fat.ordinal^4	-695.3781	331.1917	-2.100
fat.ordinal^5	-406.8785	177.2096	-2.296
fat.ordinal^6	-157.7968	76.7219	-2.057
fat.ordinal^7	1.7068	0.7496	2.277
WING	3.7635	1.5116	2.490
fat.ordinal.L:WING	15.2359	6.5692	2.319
fat.ordinal.Q:WING	14.8330	6.6088	2.244
fat.ordinal.C:WING	11.7161	5.2129	2.248
fat.ordinal^4:WING	7.0991	3.3809	2.100
fat.ordinal^5:WING	4.1405	1.8077	2.290
fat.ordinal^6:WING	1.6080	0.7817	2.057

Correlation matrix not shown by default, as $p = 15 > 12$.

Use `print(x, correlation=TRUE)` or
`vcov(x)` if you need it

fit warnings:

fixed-effect model matrix is rank deficient so dropping 1 column / coefficient
optimizer (nloptwrap) convergence code: 0 (OK)

boundary (singular) fit: see help('isSingular')

```
plot(simulateResiduals(mb))
```

DHARMA residual


```
# plot effect of ordinal-ranked fat score as predictor of body mass (for mean +- sd of win  
plot_model(mb, type='pred', terms='fat.ordinal', mdrt.values='meansd') +  
  theme_light() + theme(plot.title=element_blank()) +  
  labs(x='Fat score (ordinal)', y='Body mass (g)')
```

Could not compute variance-covariance matrix of predictions. No confidence intervals are returned.

Fuel deposition

Plot the raw data:

```
ggplot(mg, aes(x=Days.passed, y=Difference..g.)) +  
  geom_hline(aes(yintercept=0)) +  
  geom_point() + theme_light() +  
  scale_x_continuous(breaks=seq(1,8,1)) +  
  scale_y_continuous(breaks=seq(-4,10,2)) +  
  labs(x='Time difference between observations', y='Change in body mass (g)')
```


Add information about age & wing length, where available, and some data summaries:

```
# remove any empty spaces to allow for exact matches between tables
mg$Individual <- gsub(' ', '', mg$Individual)
stints$RINGNR <- gsub(' ', '', stints$RINGNR)

# make sure all individuals are present in the full table
all(mg$Individual %in% stints$RINGNR)
```

[1] TRUE

```
# add age class
mg$age <- unlist(lapply(mg$Individual, function(id){
  stints$Age[stints$RINGNR==id]
}))

# data are only available for juveniles
table(mg$age)
```

Juvenile
23

```
# add wing length
mg$wing <- unlist(lapply(mg$Individual, function(id){
  stints$WING[stints$RINGNR==id]
}))

# add year
mg$year <- factor(year(mg$mark.date))
# most recaptures, by far, are from 1990
table(mg$year)
```

```
1988 1989 1990 1993 1995 1999 2008
   1    2   14    1    2    2    1
```

```
# rename change in body mass
mg$mass.change <- mg$Difference..g.
```

```
summary(mg$wing)
```

```
Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.    NA's
95.0   99.0   101.0   100.4   102.0   105.0     2
```

Mixed-effects linear regression model to estimate mean mass change as a function of days between observations. Most data apoints are from 1990, but there are some data from other years as well, which is why we included year as a random factor:

```
m4 <- lmer(mass.change ~ Days.passed + (1|year), data=mg)
summary(m4)
```

```
Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']
Formula: mass.change ~ Days.passed + (1 | year)
Data: mg
```

```
REML criterion at convergence: 101.5
```

Scaled residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.1240	-0.5403	0.1318	0.4079	1.7706

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
year	(Intercept)	3.384	1.839
	Residual	4.015	2.004

Number of obs: 23, groups: year, 7

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value
(Intercept)	-1.9217	1.1272	-1.705
Days.passed	1.4352	0.3006	4.774

Correlation of Fixed Effects:

	(Intr)
Days.passed	-0.602

```
# plots for model evaluation from simulated residuals  
res.sim <- simulateResiduals(m4)  
plotQQunif(res.sim)
```



```
plotResiduals(res.sim)
```


Visualisation of model estimates along with raw data:

```
m.df <- fortify.merMod(m4)

#interact_plot() is used for convenience to show estimated effect of days between
# observations; no interaction term was present in the model
interact_plot(m4, pred='Days.passed', modx='age', plot.points=T,
              interval=T, data=m.df, colors='black') +
  geom_hline(aes(yintercept=0)) +
  theme_light() + labs(x='Days since first capture', y='Change in body mass (g)') +
  theme(legend.position='none') +
  scale_x_continuous(breaks=seq(1,8,1)) +
  scale_y_continuous(breaks=seq(-4,12,2))
```

